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KASR TARTIBLI DIFFERENSIAL OPERATORLAR UCHUN EKSTREMUM PRINSIPI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada kasr tartibli differensial operatorlar uchun ekstremum prinsipining nazariy asoslari va qo'llanilishi ko'rib chiqiladi. Kasr tartibli differensial operatorlar zamonaviy differensial tenglamalar va matematik fizika tenglamalaridagi murakkab tizimlarni modellashtirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ekstremum prinsipi yordamida bunday operatorlar bilan ifodalangan masalalarning yechimlari uchun optimal shartlar aniqlanadi. Ushbu ishda kasr tartibli differensial operatorlar uchun ekstremum prinsipi uchun asosiy teorema va lemmalar isbotlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Kasr tartibli differensial operatorlar, ekstremum prinsipi, Hopf prinsipi, differensial operatorlar, matematik modellashtirish, ekstremal masalalar.

Ushbu tenglamani o'rganamiz

$$(\operatorname{sign} y)|y|^m u_{xx} + u_{yy} + \frac{\beta_0}{y} u_y = 0, \quad (1)$$

bu yerda m va β_0 o'zgarmas sonlar bo'lib, ular uchun $m > 0$, $-\frac{m}{2} < \beta_0 < 1$ tengsizliklar o'rinli. D soha $z = x + iy$ kompleks tekisligining chekli bir bog'lamli sohasi bo'lib, $y > 0$ yarim tekisligida joylashgan va uchlari $A(-1;0)$ va $B(1;0)$ nuqtalarda bo'lgan (1) tenglamaning normal chizig'i $\sigma_0: x^2 + 4(m+2)^{-2} y^{m+2} = 1$ bilan, $y < 0$ yarim tekislikda esa (1) tenglamaning AC va BC xarakteristikalarini bilan chegaralangan bo'lsin. [1,2,3,4,5]

Musbat, kamaymaydigan $\omega(t)$ funksiya hamda $f(t)$ funksiyalar $[a,b]$ kesmada uzluksiz bo'lsin. Agar $[a,b]$ kesmada $f(t)$ funksiya o'zining musbat maksimumiga (manfiy minimumiga) $t = x$ nuqtada erishsa, $a < x < b$ va bu nuqtaning ixtiyoriy kichik

atrofida $\omega(t)f(t)$ ko'paytma $\gamma > \alpha$ ko'rsatkich bilan Gyolder shartini [2] qanoatlantirsa, u holda

$$D_{a,x}^{\alpha} \omega(x)f(x) > 0 \left(D_{a,x}^{\alpha} \omega(x)f(x) < 0 \right). \quad (2)$$

Haqiqatdan ham,

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma(1-\alpha)D_{a,x}^{\alpha} \omega f &= \Gamma(1-\alpha) \frac{d}{dx} \left[D_{a,x}^{\alpha-1} \omega(x)f(x) \right] = \\ &= \frac{d}{dx} \int_a^x \frac{\omega(t)f(t)}{(x-t)^{\alpha}} dt = \frac{d}{dx} \int_a^x \frac{\omega(t)f(t) - \omega(x)f(x)}{(x-t)^{\alpha}} dt + \frac{d}{dx} \int_a^x \frac{\omega(x)f(x)}{(x-t)^{\alpha}} dt \\ &= \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left\{ \frac{d}{dx} \int_a^{x-\varepsilon} \frac{\omega(t)f(t) - \omega(x)f(x)}{(x-t)^{\alpha}} dt + \frac{d}{dx} \int_a^{x-\varepsilon} \frac{\omega(x)f(x)}{(x-t)^{\alpha}} dt \right\} = \\ &= \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \left\{ \frac{\omega(x-\varepsilon)f(x-\varepsilon) - \omega(x)f(x)}{\varepsilon^{\alpha}} - \int_a^{x-\varepsilon} \frac{(\omega(x)f(x))'_x}{(x-t)^{\alpha}} dt - \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \alpha \int_a^{x-\varepsilon} \frac{\omega(t)f(t) - \omega(x)f(x)}{(x-t)^{1+\alpha}} dt + \int_a^{x-\varepsilon} \frac{(\omega(x)f(x))'_x}{(x-t)^{\alpha}} dt - \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \alpha \int_a^{x-\varepsilon} \frac{\omega(x)f(x)}{(x-t)^{1+\alpha}} dt + \frac{\omega(x)f(x)}{\varepsilon^{\alpha}} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Bu yerda $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ da limitga o'tib va ushbu

$$\int_a^{x-\varepsilon} \frac{\omega(x)f(x)}{(x-t)^{1+\alpha}} dt = \frac{\omega(x)f(x)}{\alpha \varepsilon^{\alpha}} - \frac{\omega(x)f(x)}{\alpha(x-a)^{\alpha}},$$

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\omega(x-\varepsilon)f(x-\varepsilon) - \omega(x)f(x)}{\varepsilon^{\alpha}} = 0,$$

tengliklarni e'tiborga olib, quyidagi tenglikka ega bo'lamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma(1-\alpha)D_{a,x}^{\alpha} \omega(x)f(x) &= \frac{\omega(x)f(x)}{(x-a)^{\alpha}} + \alpha \int_a^{\delta} \frac{\omega(x)f(x) - \omega(t)f(t)}{(x-t)^{1+\alpha}} dt + \\ &\quad + \alpha \int_{\delta}^x \frac{\omega(x)f(x) - \omega(t)f(t)}{(x-t)^{1+\alpha}} dt. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

(3) munosabatdan (2) tengsizlik kelib chiqadi.

Agar $\omega(t)$ -musbat o'smaydigan funksiya bo'lsa, yuqoridagiga o'xshash natijani $D_{x,b}^\alpha$ operator uchun ham olish mumkin.

Xopf prinsipi Ω sohada (1) tenglamaning $u(x, y)$ regulyaryechimi hech bir $(x, y) \in \Omega$ nuqtada o'zining musbat maksimumiga va manfiy minimumiga erishmaydi [2,3].

Isboti. Ushbu

$$v(x, y) = u(x, y) / A(y) \quad (4)$$

funksiyani qaraymiz, bu yerda

$$A(y) = e^{d^{1-\beta_0}} - \varepsilon e^{y^{1-\beta_0}},$$

d – bu Ω soha diametri, $0 < \varepsilon < 1$. Bevosita hisoblashlar yordamida

$$E(u) = A(y)E_1(v)$$

tenglikning to'g'riligiga ishonch hosil qilish qiyin emas, bu yerda

$$E_1(v) = y^m v_{xx} + v_{yy} + \frac{1}{y}(\beta_0 + 2yA_y)v_y + \frac{1}{A}\left(\frac{\beta_0}{y}A_y + A_{yy}\right)v, \quad (5)$$

$$A_y = -\varepsilon(1 - \beta_0)e^{y^{1-\beta_0}} y^{-\beta_0},$$

$$A_{yy} = -\varepsilon(1 - \beta_0)^2 e^{y^{1-\beta_0}} y^{-2\beta_0} + \varepsilon\beta_0(1 - \beta_0)e^{y^{1-\beta_0}} y^{-\beta_0-1},$$

$$\frac{1}{A}\left(\frac{\beta_0}{y}A_y + A_{yy}\right) = -\frac{\varepsilon}{A}(1 - \beta_0)^2 e^{y^{1-\beta_0}} y^{-2\beta_0} < 0. \quad (6)$$

(6) tengsizlikka asosan, (5) tenglama yechimi $\mathcal{G}(x, y)$ Ω soha ichidagi hech bir (x_0, y_0) nuqtada o'zining musbat maksimumiga erishmaydi. Haqiqatdan ham, teskarisini faraz qilaylik, (x_0, y_0) nuqtada $\mathcal{G}(x, y)$ funksiya o'zining musbat maksimumiga erishsin, u holda bu nuqtada

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{G}(x_0, y_0)}{\partial x} = 0, \frac{\partial \mathcal{G}(x_0, y_0)}{\partial y} = 0, \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{G}(x_0, y_0)}{\partial x^2} \leq 0, \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{G}(x_0, y_0)}{\partial y^2} \leq 0$$

bo'lgani uchun, (4) dan $E_1(\mathcal{G}) < 0$. Bu esa $E_1(\mathcal{G}) = 0$ tenglikka ziddir. Aynan shu mulohazalarni takrorlab, $\mathcal{G}(x, y)$ funksiya Ω sohaning hech bir ichki nuqtasida o'zining manfiy minimumga erishmasligini ko'rsatish mumkin.

Shunday qilib, (4) ga asosan, (1) tenglamaning regulyar yechimi $u(x, y)$ o'zining musbat maksimumi va manfiy minimumini Ω sohaning ichki nuqtalarida qabul qilmaydi.

Agar Ω sohada $u(x, y)$ funksiya:

1) $u(x, y) \in C(\bar{\Omega}) \cap C^2(\Omega)$ $E(u) \geq 0 (\leq 0)$ shartlarni qanoatlantirsa va Ω sohada o'zining eng katta musbat (eng kichik manfiy) qiymatini $(x_0, 0)$, $x_0 \in I$ nuqtada qabul qilsa,

2) $u(x, y)$ ning Γ chiziqdagi qiymati $u(x_0, 0)$ qiymatdan kichik (katta) bo'lsa, u holda

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow +0} y^{\beta_0} \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} < 0, \quad (> 0), \quad (7)$$

tengsizlik, (bu limitni mavjud bo'lishi sharti bilan) o'rinlidir.

Isboti. Musbat maksimum holini o'rganib chiqamiz. Bevosita hosila ta'rifidan,

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow +0} y^{\beta_0} \frac{\partial u(x_0, y)}{\partial y} > 0$$

tengsizlikning bajarilishi mumkin emas. Faraz qilaylik,

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow +0} y^{\beta_0} \frac{\partial u(x_0, y)}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (8)$$

bo'lsin. d orqali Ω sohaning diametrini belgilaymiz. Umumiylikni buzmasdan, $u(x_0, 0) = 1$ deb olishimiz mumkin. Lemma shartiga ko'ra, $\max_{(x, y) \in \Gamma} u(x, y) \leq 1 - \varepsilon$, bu

yerda $0 < \varepsilon < 1$. Ushbu

$$v(x, y) = u(x, y) / A(y),$$

funksiyani kiritamiz [33], bu yerda

$$A(y) = e^{d^{1-\beta_0}} - \varepsilon y^{1-\beta_0}.$$

Γ chiziqda

$$v(x, y) \leq \frac{1 - \varepsilon}{e^{d^{1-\beta_0}} - \varepsilon y^{1-\beta_0}} \leq \frac{1 - \varepsilon}{e^{d^{1-\beta_0}} (1 - \varepsilon)} < \frac{1}{e^{d^{1-\beta_0}} - \varepsilon},$$

$[-1,1]$ kesmada esa

$$v(x,0) \leq \frac{1}{e^{d^{1-\beta_0}} - \varepsilon}, \quad v(x_0,0) = \frac{1}{e^{d^{1-\beta_0}} - \varepsilon}.$$

Ushbu

$$E(u) = A(y)E_1(v), \quad (9)$$

tenglikning to'g'riligiga ishonch hosil qilish qiyin emas, bu yerda $E_1(\mathcal{G})$ (5) tenglik bilan aniqlanuvchi operator. Lemma shartiga ko'ra, (9) tenglikdan $E_1(\mathcal{G}) \geq 0$ tengsizlik kelib chiqadi. Bundan tashqari, (8) tenglikka ko'ra,

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow +0} y^{\beta_0} \frac{\partial v(x_0, y)}{\partial y} = \frac{\varepsilon(1-\beta_0)}{\left(e^{d^{1-\beta_0}} - \varepsilon\right)^2} > 0.$$

Bundan esa $(x_0,0)$ nuqtaning shunday kichik atrofi borki ($y > 0$), bu atrofda $\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} > 0$ ya'ni $v(x, y)$ funksiya bu atrofda $x = x_0$ chizig'ida o'suvchi bo'ladi va o'zining eng katta qiymatini soha ichida qabul qiladi, buning esa (6) tengsizlikka ko'ra bo'lishi mumkin emas. Yuqoridagi mulohazalarni takrorlab, manfiy minimum holini ham o'rganish mumkin.

2.1-lemma isbot bo'ldi.

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